

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

MORPHEX - A SPECTRAL MORPHING SYNTHESIZER

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Supervisor: Xavier Serra

Co-Supervisor: Baris Bozkurt

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this thesis to all my family and friends, especially to Marta, without her support and patience all this work wouldn't have been possible, heartfelt thanks for everything.

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Abstract

The main goal of this project was to find a way to perform spectral morphing while exploring the latent timbral space that emerges from the spectral analysis of musical sounds, and to craft new hybrid instruments. The project is split into two very well defined parts.

The first is research; here we have written a collection of jupyter notebooks that address the main problems that needed to be approached such as how to perform the harmonic plus magnitudes interpolations in real-time; how to manage the result of the sound analysis into a file to be able to load it afterwards on the plugin and allow the user to build their own collection of sounds and presets; how to normalize both sounds magnitudes before the synthesis and how to transpose all the harmonics of the sound properly to be able to play the sound across every note.

The second part of this project is the development of a plugin that implements all the features designed in the research part, plus designing a user interface with the proper components to allow the user to interact with the morphing engine and thus, with the generated sound.

We have ended up designing and developing a plugin that accomplishes that mission, keeping in mind that it's meant to be used professionally by producers, musicians and sound designers.

Keywords: Spectral Morphing; Spectral Analysis; Plugin; Timbre; Interactivity; Sound Design; Producers; Musicians

Chapter 1

Introduction

There has been a lot of research in sound morphing in the past, since the awesome work done in the film Farinelli[1] to Lemuri[2], a tool for timbre manipulation. Despite considering all these projects successful, we have the feeling that there are no highly interactive tools that achieves the same quality as the Farinelli work, therefore this works aims to design a proper tool that fills this gap, a very interactive, easy to use, flexible and powerful tool, we will build an audio plugin that could be launched as a standalone app or used as a plugin within a DAW (Digital Audio Workstation).

1.1 Motivation

One of the main motivations was the “*SMS Tools*”[3] software; it has a section for performing sound morphing between two sounds based on his harmonic content.

And another motivation was the singing voice of the film Farinelli[1], where a combination of two voices, a soprano and a counter-tenor, were used to cover the entire range and compensate for technical difficulties the singers may have, obtaining a very good recreation of a castrato voice.

1.2 Objectives

The main goal of this project was to find a way to perform spectral morphing while exploring the latent timbral space that emerges from the spectral analysis of musical sounds, to craft new hybrid instruments.

We have kept in mind that the final product it's meant to be used professionally by producers, musicians and sound designers.

1.3 Important Concepts

Before continuing we will mention some related concepts that you should know or at least be familiar with:

1.3.1 Timbre

As we are trying to interpolate the timbral sensations of two sound sources it is necessary to first understand what timbre is, and which meaningful information we can extract from them through the spectrogram to interpolate them in a significant way. We understand timbre as the perceived sound quality of a sound. The two main physical sound characteristics that determine the perception of timbre are the spectrum and the envelope.

1.3.2 Spectrum

The spectrum, in terms of sound, is the set of frequencies present in a sound at a certain moment in time. The visual representation of how the spectrum changes in time is a spectrogram, which can be obtained with the Fourier transform by decomposing the audio signal through time in frames with a certain window length, representing each sample of it with a sinusoid.

1.3.3 Envelope

An envelope is a function that represents the temporal evolution of the partials (sine waves) of a sound. As this wants to be a creative tool, the ADSR (Attack, Decay, Sustain and Release) of the envelope may be manually crafted by the user.

1.3.4 Morphing

Morphing is a transformation that, out of two or more elements, can generate new ones with hybrid properties[4]. How that morphing is performed is up to the designer, in our case, we will be interpolating values between audio features.

1.3.5 Interpolation

Interpolation is a way of constructing new data points within the range of a discrete set of known data points, in our case, the data points will be concrete values within a vector in a range from 20 Hz to 20 kHz (the frequency range of human hearing).

1.3.6 Interactivity

With interactivity, we mean that the interaction between the user and the tool must be very fluent. The tool must provide enough feedback, either through visuals or the own tool's interface, to help the user understand what is happening to the sound and make it easier to achieve the desired effect or transformation. Thus the interface design is very important to accomplish that goal.

1.4 Jupyter Notebook

Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that provides you with an interactive work environment. It allows you to develop Python code in a very dynamic way; you can build blocks of code, text, and graphics into the same document.

We have chosen this framework to carry out our research tasks for two main reasons:

The first one is that it has become very popular among the research community, so it's easy to find a lot of tools, forums, resources and other notebooks too that may help you to success on your tasks.

And second, we have personally used this framework before and it has repeatedly demonstrated to us that it is very capable and powerful. Furthermore, we already have experience using it, so we will perform faster with it than if using other frameworks.

1.5 JUCE

JUCE is a C++ cross-platform open-source framework. It's free to use as long as you do not build commercial products with it, in that case, you need to buy a license. We have chosen to develop the plugin with this framework for a lot of reasons.

It's written in C++ so it's very fast, and when dealing with audio time waits for nothing, so this is a very important aspect.

It works just out of the box, it's an easy framework to start developing audio tools, it's well documented and it comes with a lot of examples, so you do not start from zero. It comes with a lot of classes that you can override and rewrite it to do whatever you want to achieve, the only thing you need to know it's to find out (using the documentation) what class do the specific task you want to change and put your code on it. It provides a lot of built-in functions and modules that can help you through the process of developing an audio plugin such as an FFT class, an ADSR class, and a MIDI class, so you can focus on developing the core features

of your plugin and use the built-in classes to perform everything else which is pretty handy.

It seems that in the last few years it's being more and more used, so that means more support, more community, and more code examples.

And of course its cross-platform feature, you can write the code once and compile build for different platforms such as macOS, Windows and Linux, and in different formats, like VST, VST3, AU, and a standalone app (".app" for macOS, and ".exe" for Windows). So this is will be very helpful to be able to maintain the project in the future.

1.6 State of the Art

1.6.1 SMS Tools

As we are basing our work on the “*SMS Tools*”[3] it is mandatory to cite the work done by Serra, X. in Musical sound modeling with sinusoids plus noise [5], which expose a lot of concepts that are directly implemented into the SMS Tools like peak detection and continuation, pitch detection, stochastic analysis and stochastic approximation among other. This work also inherits from “*A system for sound analysis/transformation/synthesis based on a deterministic plus stochastic decomposition*”[6], a system that is already implemented into SMS Tools.

This last reference, besides being a very a good source for knowing the analysis/transformation/synthesis paradigm, is very important for us for many reasons, we can find a lot of concepts that are also present in “*SMS Tools*” and, therefore, in our tool:

- It uses additive synthesis is used to generate the deterministic part of the signal (the harmonics), we will generate them the same way.
- It exposes a way to bring back the stochastic component (the noise) that we are losing when performing the harmonic detection, the stochastic part of the signal is generated by performing the inverse Fourier transform with the spectral envelopes of the original sounds applied to generated noise.

We must mention “*Sound Hybridization on a deterministic plus stochastic decomposition model*”[7] which describes the sound hybridization (also known as morphing) system based on the STFT; despite this kind of hybridization is not present in our tool it would be convenient to explore adding it as a feature.

1.6.2 Lemur

Figure 1: Lemur’s analysis of a violin sound, you can modify the sinusoidal tracks with a using point-click-and-drag mousing

Lemur, a tool for timbre manipulation [2], is a tool that allows you to analyze a sound and modify its harmonic content (see Figure 1), the tool also allows you to morph the harmonic content of two previously analyzed sounds, however, you cannot do it in real-time. They say that “A real-time controllable implementation of a bandwidth-enhanced synthesis algorithm is under development.”, however, they said so a long ago and we don’t have any news about it, so we come to fill that gap.

1.6.3 Audio Plugins

As we are building an audio plugin, it is mandatory to explore other audio plugins that are out in the market that are an example of creativity. So we will mention some plugins that manipulate the audio in very creative ways.

Iris 2 (iZotope)

Figure 2: iZotope’s Iris 2 sample-based synthesizer

Iris 2 allows you to generate sound by playing up to four audio files at once allowing you to layer them and mix them however you want.

The main characteristic of this plugin, and that makes it unique, is that it displays the spectrogram of the sample letting you manipulate it by “painting” in filters, unlocking creative filtering possibilities that would be impossible with traditional synthesizer controls.

MORPH 2 (Zynaptiq)

Figure 3: Zynaptiq's MORPH 2 real-time structural audio morphing plugin

According to their website, MORPH 2 is a real-time plug-in for structural audio morphing, the sonic equivalent of one object slowly changing its shape to become a different object.

As you can see they do not explain exactly how the morphing is done, but we can guess it may use the envelope of the sound 1, and applies it to the sound 2; obviously, it's probably not that simple because their results are far that. We have used this plugin in sound design and its creative possibilities are amazing.

It would be nice to know the details about how the 5 different morphing algorithms have been made but, understandably, they do not share this information at all. Apart from what we have mentioned about the use of envelopes to morph between sounds, looking at the GUI, we can deduce that formant filters are also implied in the morphing process, but we can't go much further.

Turnado (Sugar Bytes)

Figure 4: Sugar Bytes's Turnado audio-mangler plugin

Turnado is an all-in-one audio mangler, this plugin comes with 24 audio effects such as "tonalizer", "vocodizer", "granulizer", stutter, and vowel filter among others.

Besides the huge amount of effects, another thing that makes it great as a creative tool is the way you use it and how you can control it; you can browse through a library of presets where each of them is a combination of 8 of any of these 24 effects, you can control them by using any of the 8 knobs it has or control all 8 effects simultaneously with a single fader.

1.7 Summary

After reading this chapter, you know the motivations that have taken us to start this project and which are our main objectives. We have said that will be using Jupyter Notebook (Python) to carry out our research tasks, and for developing the plugin we will use JUCE (C++). All the concepts, frameworks and languages that have been used along the project has been introduced, so after reading this chapter you should have a nice picture of the context the project has been made.

Also we have made a review about the state of the art, we have seen “*SMS Tools*”[3], the software we are basing our work on, and a piece of software called “*Lemur*”[2], a program that perform harmonic morphing but not it’s not very accessible for musicians and producers to actually use it in their sound design sessions nor compositions.

And finally, we have overviewed three audio plugins that, they are clearly different between them, but all success in manipulating audio in a very creative and original way, and making it very accessible for musicians an easy to use.

Chapter 2

Methodology

Spectral Modeling Synthesis Tools, also known as “*SMS Tools*”[3], is the software our work will be based on. We will focus on the transformations part, more specifically on the one called harmonic plus stochastic morphing, this will be our starting point. This transformation morphs two sounds using the short-time Fourier transform to analyse the sounds, then it resamples the signal to generate a morphed smooth spectrum of the two sounds.

The methodology is as follows, first, we design, write and test everything in jupyter notebooks, when the code works as expected the next phase is to implement this block of python code into the C++ application. This methodology will be applied, not only for the core part of the project, which is the sound morphing algorithm, but for any other feature of the plugin. First, we will see the diagrams of the two main applications that we will develop, one to perform the sound analysis (generates a ".had" file), and another one to perform the morphing and the synthesis (reads a ".had" file).

The context is as follows, first we need to understand how the harmonic plus stochastic transformation of “*SMS Tools*”[3] works, redesign it so we can change the parameters of the morphing (harmonics, magnitudes, and stochastic) and synthesize the result all in real-time, and think a way to transpose the two sounds that we are morphing so the resulting sound targets the desired note in a keyboard.

2.1 Diagrams

Figure 5: Sound Analysis and Spectral Morphing Tool diagrams

We must think of this as a product that will consist of two main parts, if we take a look at our two diagrams 5 we see that, in one hand we have the “Sound Analyzer” to analyze the sounds and generate the “.had” files, so the sounds get ready to be loaded into the morphing plugin, this “Sound Analyzer” is only meant to be used by advanced users that want to generate their own sounds and use them in the plugin, we will talk about that a bit later, and on the other hand the actual plugin, called “Spectral Morphing Tool”.

2.2 Mockups

As mentioned in the previous section, by the end of the project, we will have 2 main outputs:

- The first one will be a jupyter notebook that analyses the sound and generates a ".had" file that contains the results of those analyses.
- The second one is the audio plugin that will load these ".had" files, perform the sound morphing, and synthesize the result.

So before start, we made a mockup for each of these 2 applications.

2.2.1 Analysis Tool Mockup

inputFile1: ... >

window1: M1: N1: t1:

minSineDur1: minf01: maxf01:

f0et1: harmDevSlope1:

Figure 6: Sound Analysis mockup

This sound analysis tool is our first step, and it will look very similar to the one present on the SMS Tools. It will have almost the same functionality.

Our methodology was to do jupyter notebooks that, step by step, get closer to the Spectral Morphing Tool (now called Morphex) plugin mockup 7, so the final jupyter notebook will be a working prototype with the core functionalities of Morphex. All the other features are done in separated jupyter notebooks.

2.2.2 Spectral Morphing Tool Plugin Mockup

Figure 7: Spectral Morphing Tool plugin mockup

The second mockup is the audio plugin. Even though the final plugin doesn't look exactly like this mockup, almost all the main components are already there, such as a central XY pad, two windows where you can see the sounds you have loaded, and a tabbed component between them just to keep some extra parameters and features. Below these two waveforms displays, there is room for future parameters that will affect and modulate the sound, some of these parameters are mentioned in the future work section. For the Jupyter Notebook's prototype is not required to have an XY-pad, only sliders that give the same functionality, we will work more on the GUI on the C++ development phase. Also for the moment, we will focus on having the main functionality, which means that only linear interpolation will be available for now.

2.3 Harmonic Interpolation

Figure 8: In red, the harmonics taken from Sound 1 that will be interpolated with the harmonics taken from Sound 2

The first step in our research process is to perform harmonic interpolation, we will perform it in the same way as it is done in “*SMS Tools*”[3]; the first taken harmonic of the sound 1 will be linearly interpolated with the first taken harmonic of the sound 2, the second with the second and so on. It is important to know how the interpolation is done right now so we can start thinking about new and creative ways to interpolate these harmonics.

Our task here was to understand how this process work, and adapt this part of the “*SMS Tools*”[3] into a jupyter notebook so we can continue building our project on top of this. As the interpolation in “*SMS Tools*”[3] is not done in real-time, we need to rewrite this code with the idea of performing this interpolation in real-time, as now that we have adapted and understood this algorithm, we can do a real-time version of it by using a circular buffer.

2.4 Circular Buffer

Figure 9: Snapshot of the synthesis in the 100th frame of the harmonics array

Now that we know how to perform the harmonic interpolation, we need to design a way to do it using a circular buffer, so let's see how we did it. Let's take a look into a snapshot of the circular buffer in context, if we look at the Figure 9 we can see three colours that belong to three different pointers, each section does the following:

- **Clean Section (Red):** It puts the following samples (128 in this example) of the buffer to zero, as we are applying a window and summing in the yellow section, if we don't do that the sound will end up being "clipped" after some iterations.
- **Write Section (Yellow):** In this example, the write section has a length of 512, it performs the synthesis using a window and it makes hops of 128 each time.
- **Play Section (Green):** Once the write section has completed written 512 samples, the play pointer gets these samples and writes it to the output buffer so we can hear the result.

Now we are able to perform harmonic interpolation in real-time but, this can't be played on a MIDI keyboard, right now the output is an interpolation of the

two samples, so the output frequency will only be determined by the frequency interpolation factor, so if this factor is 0.5, the resulting frequency for each harmonic will be just in the middle of the harmonics of the sound 1, and the equivalent harmonic of the sound 2; so to fix this we must find a way to transpose all the harmonic to target the desired note.

2.5 Harmonic Transposition

Figure 10: All the harmonics of the sound "violin-B3" that we need to transpose. As we have said in the previous section, we want our plugin to be played, and for that we need a way to map one single sound to the whole keyboard, which comprehends 128 possible notes between C-1 and G9, but we won't be thinking in notes, we will think in frequencies, so that way we can output any possible tone; with this approach we will let the user perform pitch bend if desired. To do so, we need to transpose all the harmonics by a factor, and we have found two different approaches to solve the problem.

2.5.1 Fundamental Tracking

Figure 11: Transposed harmonics of the sound "violin-B3" targeting a 440 Hz note, using the fundamental tracking approach

To show how the harmonics transposition is done in this approach we will use the sound "violin-B3", which is violin playing the B3 note. We have a vector of frames, each frame contains all the harmonics that were found in the analysis stage.

In this approach, we divide all the harmonics of the current frame by the fundamental frequency of that frame, then we multiply all the harmonics for the target frequency that we want to achieve (in this example, 440 Hz).

You can see resulting harmonics by applying this process to all the 743 frames that contain the ".had" file of the sound "violin-B3" in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Resulting fundamental when applying the fundamental tracking approach

The problem with this approach is that, although the transposed harmonics match perfectly the target note, the timbre changes too much. As we can see in Figure 14, the resulting fundamental is completely flat.

This result may not be the desired one when transposing harmonics from natural/organic sounds "such as a violin or a voice", but we have observed that it may produce a very interesting result when applied to electronic sounds, so we have decided to maintain the code in the app and make this harmonic transposition option available in the near future.

2.5.2 Predominant Note

Figure 13: Transposed harmonics of the sound "violin-B3" targeting a 440 Hz note, using the predominant note approach

This is the approach for harmonic transposition that we have working as default in the final version of the plugin. When a sound is loaded by the plugin, we perform feature extraction on it to obtain relevant information that may be used later on. Right now the only feature extracted is the predominant note, which simply generates a sorted list with the number of occurrences of each note of the fundamental along all the harmonics frames of a sound.

This is a very good approach because, as we are using the harmonic model on the analysis stage, a true predominant note may be found. This will result in a very good transposition of the sound to any target frequency.

Figure 14: Resulting fundamental when applying the predominant note approach

And as we see in Figure 14, the resulting fundamental keeps the same shape and properties of the original one, so the timbre is not being affected that much when using this approach. So to conclude, the best way to transpose the harmonics is using this one, the predominant note approach, but use the fundamental tracking can lead to very unexpected and interesting results.

2.6 Summary

In this chapter we have seen our methodology, let's go over it point by point:

1. Generate two diagrams (one for each tool) so we have a clear idea of how these tools will be made.
2. Draw two mockups (also one for each tool) so we have clear what parameters do we need and how the final user interface will look like.
3. Understand how the harmonic morphing algorithm works.
4. Redesign the harmonic morphing algorithm so it can perform in real-time with the help of a circular buffer.
5. Design a way to make the instrument playable, so the harmonics of both sounds are transposed to target the desired note before entering the harmonic morphing algorithm.

As you can see, now we have all it's needed to develop the actual audio plugin, so with the results of our research stage now we can enter the development stage and build our spectral morphing tool.

Chapter 3

Results

The section in this chapter shows the most relevant output of the project, jupyter notebooks from the research stage and the final audio plugin.

3.1 Sound Analysis

Figure 15: A Jupyter Notebook called "Sound Analysis", where the .had files are generated

As the first result of our research stage, we have a notebook called "Sound Analysis". This is a recreation of the transformations GUI present in the “*SMS Tools*”[3], as you can see the parameters are the same. The main difference here is that when you have analyzed a sound you can generate a ".had" file of that sound; we will read that file later on the plugin to load all the needed information to perform a resynthesis of the sound. The ".had" contains metadata about the sound file analyzed, the frequencies of all the harmonics, their magnitudes, and their phases. This is all the information that the audio plugin will need to perform the morphing and the synthesis.

3.2 Tool Recreation

Figure 16: The "Tool Recreation" Jupyter Notebook is a recreation of the SMS Tools interface that reads the .had files to generate the morphs

We have implemented the HPS (harmonic plus stochastic) GUI of the “*SMS Tools*”[3] to have a starting point and, from here, begin to add more interactivity, the new GUI with more controls, live audio morphing and new features. For the moment the "Harmonic Frequencies", "Harmonic Magnitudes" and "Stochastic Component", are inputs were you can type time and value pairs that will be sent to the SMS Tools models to generate the morphing.

3.3 Live Morphing

Figure 17: The "Live Morphing" Jupyter Notebook shows how the interpolation and the synthesis are done frame by frame and how the circular buffer works.

The "Live Morphing" is the 4th of our Jupyter Notebooks, the third it's only an experiment of the interaction between audio and ipywidgets so we will not explain it here. This notebook is a full integration of all the previous notebooks, from the first to the third, it shows how the interpolation and the synthesis are done frame by frame and how the circular buffer works. This is the core of the plugin, we will need to adapt this code to C++ and make it work inside the JUCE framework.

3.4 Spectral Morphing Tool

Figure 18: Version 0.1 of the plugin called "Spectral Morphing Tool"

Figure 18 shows a screenshot of the version 0.1 of the plugin, at that moment the plugin was simply named "Spectral Morphing Tool". In this version we only had working the core of the project, which is:

- Read the .had files.
- Perform the morphing between two preloaded sounds ("violin-B3" and "soprano-E4").
- Get the parameters from the GUI to control the morphing and apply them in real-time.
- Synthesize the output of the morphing in a continuous stream.

We have tried not to use any external library to keep everything inside the JUCE Framework ecosystem (i.e. XML, mathematics, filesystem, etc.).

Figure 19: Version 0.2 of the plugin, now called Morphex

3.5 Morphex

Figure 19 shows a screenshot of the version 0.2 of the plugin, now renamed to "Morphex". This is a list of all the features that are on this final version:

- Morphing the harmonics of two sounds (frequencies + magnitudes).
- Methods of harmonic transposition to be able to play the instrument ("Real Fundamental Tracking" and "Predominant Fundamental Normalization").
- Feature extraction of the sounds (by now, only the predominant fundamental).
- Magnitudes normalization (pre-synthesis).

- Design and implementation of the graphical interface.
- XY pad component to explore and control the matrix interpolation.
- MIDI control over the synthesis engine of the plugin.
- Automations of the parameters of the plugin from a DAW.
- Be able to load sounds "on the fly" with a browser using the left and right arrow keys on the keyboard.
- Polyphony up to 5 simultaneous voices.
- Preset management system (new, load and save).

We have compiled 3 different builds of the plugin:

- A standalone app for macOS (you can open it directly).
- An Audio Unit plugin "AU" (for you DAW).
- And a "VST3" plugin (also for you DAW).

Unfortunately, they are only for macOS, we couldn't get a valid build for Windows on time. To use the VST3 or AU builds, you must put the ".vst3" file in your VST3 plugins folder (same for AU), open your VST3/AU compatible DAW, scan your plugins folder and load the plugin. On the first run, the plugin will create a folder on your desktop called "Morphex". Inside there are two folders; "Collections", where the sounds are located, and "Presets". Replace those folders with the ones located in the ".zip". You can load sounds on the fly with the sound browser using the left and right arrows of your keyboard, left to load sound 1 and right to load sound 2.

As a negative part, first, the ADSR parameters do not work well, so this issue needs to be addressed in the near future; and second, the synthesis of the stochastic component does not work correctly, everything is implemented but it does not work

as expected, so this feature needs a bit more of effort to make it work. As a final note, the pitch bend has stopped working when adding the 5 voices, this will also be arranged the sooner the better.

Usability

So, now we have the plugin, how can we use it? We have tried the plugin with many sounds, in many situations and applying different effects, just like you will do when producing your own music within a DAW. So these are some of cases that we have found to use the tool in a creative way:

- Create hybrid instruments like a violin crossed with a flute, it's nice to have this mixture, you can achieve very interesting results, especially if you move the XY pad in up and down from (0,0) to (1,1) while the notes are playing.
- Cross instruments with the human voice like a violin crossed with a soprano, you can get very interesting results if you move the XY pad from the violin to the soprano like if it was a "vibrato" at the end of the note; and if you do so when playing a chord, and add a reverb, the result is gorgeous, very usable in a composition actually.
- Another interesting experiment is to morph a very harmonic sound with a percussive one such as a snare, the resulting sounds are very harsh and crispy, especially if you move the XY pad around the upper left corner.

We are sure that if you experiment with the plugin will find out very strange yet great sounds and combinations, especially if you add your own sounds to your sound collection.

3.6 Repositories

We have ended up splitting the project into to separated repositories, one for the research part called one called “*Morphex Research*”[8], and another one for the plugin development simply called “*Morphex*”[9], we will describe them in more detail in the next two sections. You can find the link to the repositories in the bibliography of this thesis.

Morphex Research

This is the research repository, it contains 4 folders:

- **data:** in the subfolder called (sounds) there are all the sounds that we have used to test the notebook "1 - Sound Analysis", the other folder called "analysis_output" stores the results of those analyses.
- **externals:** it contains the version of the “*SMS Tools*”[3] used with this project.
- **notebooks:** where all the research notebooks are located.
- **scripts:** it contains some scripts that Docker need to build the docker container image.

The other files "Dockerfile", "docker-compose.yml", and "requirements.txt" are also used by docker to build the docker image and to run the docker container. It is especially interesting the file called "requirements.txt" as it contains all the dependencies of the project.

For further information and to find out how to set up and run this project, you can lead to the "README.md" file, it contains everything you need to know to do so.

Morphex

This is the development repository, the project structure is the typical one in a JUCE project:

- **Assets:** contains images and sounds that are embedded in the application.
- **Builds:** once you compile the project, the resulting binaries are stored here.
- **JuceLibraryCode:** it contains some files generated by the "Projucer" (the JUCE's project generator), they are needed by the JUCE framework.
- **Source:** it contains all the code that has been developed through this project.

The "Morphex.jucer" it's meant to be opened by the "Projucer" application, then you must select a target IDE (i.e. Xcode or Visual Studio), and it will automatically generate a project with our "source" files so you can compile it.

For further information and to find out how to set up and run this project, you can lead to the "README.md" file, it contains everything you need to know to do so.

3.7 Summary

In this chapter we have seen all the results we have obtained, all the relevant jupyter notebooks, a first audio plugin that only had the morphing algorithm working, and the final audio plugin version.

All the Python code in the jupyter notebooks has been ported to C++, and using the JUCE framework to process this code, generate a UI and compile the project, we have been able to obtain the audio plugin that we were looking for.

Also, we have talked about the repositories, one for research and the other one for the audio plugin, what they contain and what you need to do if you want to set up the projects and have them running.

Chapter 4

Conclusions

4.1 Discussion

4.1.1 User Testing

For the user testing, we prepared a ".zip" containing the plugin in three different binaries: ".app", ".vst3" and ".component". The zip also contains a PDF with all the instructions to get the plugin up and running and a link to a Google Form that they should fulfill once they are done testing the plugin. In summary, we have asked our users for the following:

- First impressions after using the plugin.
- About the features the plugin offers:
 - Enough number of features (from 1 to 10).
 - Quality of these features (from 1 to 10).
 - Any feature you would like to see implemented? (open question).
- About the performance of the plugin:
 - Overall performance of the plugin (open question).

- How many instances of the plugin have you run at the same time? (from 1 to 10).
- Overall performance of the plugin (from 1 to 10).
- About the quality of the plugin:
 - Thoughts regarding sound quality (open question).
 - Rate the sound quality (from 1 to 10).
- Usefulness, ease of use and suggestions:
 - How useful did you found the plugin for your sound design, music production and/or creative process? (from 1 to 10).
 - How easy to use did you found the plugin? (from 1 to 10).
 - Have you faced any problems while using the plugin? (open question).
 - Do you have any suggestion, feature or improvement? (open question).

Their answers will help us to shape some aspects of the following sections. In general, the feedback has been very positive, even though we have found some issues that have decreased the user experience, so some bugs need to be addressed.

4.1.2 Features

As we have seen before we have implemented all the features needed to perform morphing between two sounds, control the way the morphing is done with an XY pad and make the result playable with a MIDI keyboard. The plugin also comes with some pre-analysed sounds and presets so the user can use it just out of the box. One interesting feature will be for example to allow the user to design new ways and patterns to interpolate the harmonics in a more complex way, this will increment the interest for the tool. We will see that feature and much more on the future work section, having all those features will increment the plugin's creative possibilities. About the users, some of them say that needs more features to be very useful, and they complain about the ADSR not being implemented yet.

4.1.3 Performance

As for performance, first we need to state the hardware specifications of our machine, we have been using an iMac (Mid 2011) with an Intel Core i5-2500S @ 2.70GHz. Regarding the plugin, now it uses a 2% CPU synthesizing the 5 voices at the same time; the use of CPU increases to 5% if in addition to the 5 voices you also move the XY pad. As you can see, 5% of CPU load allows you to have multiple instances of the plugin running at the same time, which is suitable for a music production environment using a DAW. We have corroborated with other users that when you play notes very quickly you can hear a bit of crackling, although we don't know if this is a performance issue, further investigation it's needed to solve that problem.

4.1.4 Quality

Right now we are not adding the stochastic part, we are losing part of the original sound. Audio quality is good, but it will be evaluated by user testing. Evaluate the quality of the morphing is hard, mostly because there is a subjective factor, however, it will also be evaluated by user testing. Explore more in-depth and implement techniques for voice morphing would add value to the tool. And also creating a model for harmonic transposition that would make voice samples sound more realistic in the lower and highest octaves would be a very nice addition to the plugin. Users agree that in general terms, the quality of the morphing is very good.

4.1.5 Usefulness

This part is subjective too, and it depends on the final user, so to evaluate if the tool is useful or not user testing is also required. We have found it very useful when looking for original sounds to stand out in your productions, but there are some minor issues like multi instantiability problems within a DAW that may be addressed to make it fully functional and useful. In general, the users say that the tool helps to create new interesting sounds, but the fact that we have found a problem with multi instantiation (only sounds one instance of the plugin at a time on some DAWs), makes it a bit hard to use extensively in a project.

4.1.6 Ease of use

An XY pad has been added, this makes exploring this latent timbral space (see how this latent space is built in the chapter “*Results*”, section “*Morphex*”) easier and more enjoyable. Another point is that right now to add your own sounds to the plugin is not that easy, and requires the user to have a certain knowledge about the matter, with the technology we have today (i.e. Deep Learning), we could try to automate the harmonic analysis part that right now must be done within the jupyter notebook. The tool also needs some visual feedback to know what’s happening to the harmonics. In the user testing we have seen that, regarding the XY pad, a label or an icon would have helped to make clearer what each axis does. Also, one user has had problems with the installation process regarding the creation of folders, so making an installable would get rid of that kind of problems.

4.2 Future Work

We have an idea of how this project could be extended in the future. A great feature will be to perform automatic harmonic analysis on audio files, by drag and drop dropping a sound or just using the file browser. Another great feature that would make the plugin more useful is to perform live automatic harmonic analysis of two audio input streams, so to speak, two channels of the DAW hosting the plugin. Another interesting feature will be, when loading audio files, to let the user interpolate between the attack and decay envelopes of both sounds and be able to play notes on the piano with this interpolation; when interpolating live audio input, show ADSR parameters. Also add more complex ways of morphing between the harmonics, rather than only allow the user to perform linear interpolation.

As we have more interesting features we have decided to put them in a list:

- Add the possibility to perform the sound analysis right on the plugin.
- Try to simplify all the parameter analysis into a single XY map (or heat map) si it’s easier to perform a good sound analysis when generating .had files.

- Add a tab where you can browse and retrieve sounds from “*freesound*”[10] directly and download it to create a sound (analysis, region selection, etc), also save the author the link and all the relevant information inside the .had file.
- Just above the midi keyboard on the GUI, add two sliders to let the user map the sound 1 and the sound 2 across the keyboard doing a crossfade so, depending on the note/key that the user plays, sound 1 will be more present (i.e. 0.8 than sound 2), so if we join that with legato (done between harmonics) and adjusting the pitch of the sound 1 and 2 to sound on key, it will be a very useful feature.
- Add a “sample pack designer” option in a new tab or section inside the plugin, so the user will be able to create their own sample packs.
- Add envelopes inside the plugin to automate parameters (one shot and loop).
- Right now the output is mono, decorrelate the audio to generate stereo (and add some FX like delay, reverb and dimension expander).
- We have the harmonics of the sounds, that means that we could change the scale, play chords, make chorus and more.
- Make the waveform visualization look the same way as it is done in freesound.
- Add a vibrato (simple at the moment, just say the number of milliseconds till start the vibrato and the amplitude).
- Add the ability to select various regions on a single sample file to be able to map them across the keyboard, the map will be done automatically, as we know the fundamental, it will be mapped through the keyboard till the half of the next sample is mapped on the keyboard (it would be nice to have other interpolation curves rather than made it just linear), this way we make much easier to map an entire instrument sampler like, corrections will be applied depending on the note we are mapping to keep it good sounding good / realistic (harmonic transposition methods).

- Add a button to perform interpolation between those regions on the keyboard depending on the note you are playing.
- When allowing to select more than one region on the waveform visualization to be mapped on the keyboard, add a button to "hide" on the visualization the regions of the sound that are not selected because they won't sound so it doesn't make sense to show them then.
- Make the .had file a compressed tile type (i.e. zip) this way the collections will not be so heavy.
- Add a parameter to allow change the speed of the sound playback.
- Design an algorithm that, with the sound envelope, translates this values into ADSR values, we can do linear interpolation later between the ADSR values of sound 1 and the ADSR values of sound 2.
- With the envelope of the sound, maybe we can "normalize" the amplitude to make it "flat" and then apply our custom ADSR parameters.
- Add support for MPE and MIDI 2.0, it will make the instrument more expressive.
- Add a minimalistic/live mode, where only the XY pad is displayed an everything else is collapsed or accessible like if you were using the app on a phone.
- Explore the possibility to make a phone app.

We have worked more on the technical side thus a lot of work is yet to be done on the creative aspect of the plugin like think new ways to interact with the sound morphing process.

4.3 Final Thoughts

The plugin has been made and it performs its main goal successfully, morph the harmonics of two sounds. It's true that, at the time of writing these lines, we are missing the stochastic part but, apart from being likely to be done soon, we found that the plugin itself it's pretty useful in its current conditions. The people that I have shared the audio plugin with, told me that they had very fun so far with it, even though it's evident that this product is on its first iteration, so there is a lot of room for improvements and addition of new features.

We have decided to go open-source with the whole project, both research, and development. We are convinced that sharing this project with the community will help people that want to know how the process of making a plugin is done. Furthermore, if more experienced people contribute to this project, all the improvements may be eventually accomplished.

You can find a copy of the code in the following two repositories; for the research part done in python you can head to the "*Morphex Research*"[8] repository, it contains all the material needed to reproduce our research environment and run all the code successfully; if you want to download the version of the code that was submitted along with this thesis you can head to the commit called "Master Thesis Submission" that dates on September 2019. for the development part done with JUCE in C++ you can go to the "*Morphex*"[9] repository, there you will find all the information needed to compile and run Morphex; and if you want to download the version of the code that was submitted along with this thesis you can head to the commit also called "Master Thesis Submission" that dates on September 2019.

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